

User Personas Collected in preparation of a HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 project proposal

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Introduction and methodology

In the fight against climate change, the development of effective adaptation strategies and plans is crucial. Knowing this, we are preparing a project proposal for the [HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 call](#), with the goal to identify needs and design scientifically sound climate adaptation strategies.

To accomplish this, we have set out to develop a series of detailed personas that reflect the diverse perspectives of those involved in climate change adaptation. By putting ourselves in the shoes of these personas, we aim to better understand the specific needs and challenges faced in addressing this global issue.

This exercise is not theoretical - it is strongly grounded in empirical data. Indeed, in preparation for this task, we engaged in extensive interviews with a wide range of stakeholders, each providing valuable input and insights. In agreement with the interviewees, we have chosen to detail the results of these interviews as personas and preserve their anonymity. The names we used in the personas are all fictitious.

This document presents these personas, aimed at helping us to design and implement more effective climate change adaptation strategies and plans. Each persona comes from a unique angle, yet all share a common goal - confronting and overcoming the multifaceted impacts of climate change. For each of these personas, we also highlight their needs. In the project proposal we wrote, we linked these needs to the project objectives e.g. to FAIR and open data sharing in support of the mission adaptation to climate change. Their different needs and experiences will guide and inspire us as we shape the future of climate change adaptation.

Personas & their corresponding needs

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Specialist

Lucia works with an NGO that advises local authorities in Venice on adaptation measures necessary for the historical city due to projected sea level rise and inadequate foundations it is built on. To provide an integrated assessment with indicators that take into account environmental, engineering,

economic, and social factors, Lucia needs to integrate heterogeneous data collected by diverse stakeholders ranging from research, city planning and industry. Due to enormous frictions in data infrastructures, Lucia and her team spend far too much of their time on finding relevant data, which is typically not indexed in a publicly accessible data repository; on understanding data, as parameter semantics and metadata more generally are often intelligible only to experts or missing altogether, thus requiring time-consuming one-to-one interactions with data collectors; on data preprocessing, as data come in numerous formats ranging from text to binary and rely on various transformations such as units in order for the data to be ready for analysis. FAIR data is key to reduce the enormous friction in current data infrastructures and, thus, minimise the cost of data collection and preprocessing and thereby empower our ability for accelerated implementation of climate adaptation measures.

Lucia needs:

- Local and eventually regional data about:
 - Climate data (historical and future trends): precipitation, temperature, sea level rise;
 - Geospatial data: elevation data (topography), land use, land cover;
 - Building & infrastructure (existing with information on their current conditions, and planned): buildings, bridges, roads, and other critical infrastructure, water supply, drainage systems;
 - Ecological data: biodiversity (flora and fauna), ecological sensitivity (maps indicating areas of ecological importance or vulnerability);
 - Socio-economic data: population (demographic data to understand the distribution and density of the population), economic indicators (activities, industries, and employment), property values, insurance claims (if possible related to climate events);
 - Hazard data (historical and future trends): extreme weather events (storms, floods or heat waves), disasters (past events and their impacts on the region);
 - Health data: Information on health issues related to climate change, such as heat-related illnesses or vector-borne diseases;
- Previous adaptation projects/initiatives
- Mitigation strategies and plans in place in the regions: information on efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the region;
- Community:
 - surveys/assessments on the community's perception of vulnerability and resilience;
 - Communication channels: social networks, community structures, etc. to understand what are the most efficient communication channels;
- Infrastructure:
 - Lucia conducts her analyses using her laptop. Her NGO recognizes the importance of using open source; they transitioned from ArcGIS Pro to QGIS a few years ago. A few members of her team can implement and/or use code snippets in Python in QGIS. However, most of the processing is done directly with QGIS and Excel. Some members of her team found this change challenging, and they still have some lingering concerns about the transition. She is not familiar with cloud computing and believes it may not be secure enough to host the data received from some stakeholders. All the data is stored in-house e.g. on local disks and multiple copies of the same data can be found on different disks because the data is stored per project. Everything is archived in-house. This is important for Lucia and her team as all the

stakeholders involved fully trust her and her methods. She is very concerned about storing data on the cloud.

Climate modelling research scientist

Dr. Leila Khalil is an experienced Climate Research Scientist working at the Norwegian Meteorological Service, specialising in the COordinated Regional climate Downscaling EXperiment (CORDEX). With a focus on applying rigorous and scientifically recognised downscaling techniques, Dr. Khalil and her team publish data on the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) with comprehensive metadata and open. The published data follow standardised conventions, using agreed variable names and CF-Conventions, ensuring ease of use and comparability to observations. Working with the NorESM Earth System Model for CMIP6 global data is challenging and still involves many manual processes which can cause delays. Leila aims to automate workflows but faces time and skill constraints. Frustrations mounted as Norwegian CORDEX data, tailored for Nordic countries, is underutilised by consultancies opting for non-Nordic data, potentially impacting the accuracy of climate adaptation plans. She is hoping this EU call can help to streamline the entire process from the generation of global climate data with NorESM to regional climate data, and is therefore interested in the concept of FAIR software and FAIR workflow. She believes that if it becomes easier to run global climate experiments and streamline downscaling to regional data then they could also work with consultancies on more customised climate mitigation scenarios which would also help to develop and implement more accurate climate adaptation strategies and plans. However, she is reluctant in engaging in this EU call because she strongly believes that making data FAIR will be difficult and time consuming, and will add more delays to the generation of regional climate data.

Dr. Leila Khalil needs:

- Global CMIP6 data, or other global climate data generated by researchers and based on specific scenarios (for instance agreed with consultancies and/or regions);
- Global climate models are run on powerful HPC but some smaller tests could be done on any platforms if bit reproducibility is guaranteed. Containers have been made available to the NorESM community but it is hard to find and use.
- To downscale data from global to regional, researchers need to have fast access to global climate data. For this reason, data (netCDF format) is usually downloaded from ESGF to a powerful and dedicated post processing server. The downscaling process is complex and hard to port on different machines.
- All data is open and standardisation efforts are done at international level. To make data FAIR, there is a need to coordinate at international level. For software, there are also some dependencies with external packages/software so when making FAIR software, there is a need to be able to easily do the same process every time a new version of a component is available.

Sustainability Solutions Manager

With a background in environmental science and a Master's in Sustainability Management, Erik Jansson is a dynamic Sustainability Solutions Manager with a passion for integrating environmental considerations into business strategies. With over eight years of experience in sustainability consulting, Erik is passionate about integrating environmental considerations into business

strategies. In his role, he collaborates closely with clients to understand their unique sustainability challenges, develops tailored strategies aligned with business objectives, and oversees the implementation of holistic sustainability initiatives. Erik's information-gathering approach is comprehensive, drawing insights from a variety of reputable and authoritative channels, including staying informed about the latest scientific assessments, projections, and recommendations related to climate change through the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports. He keeps abreast of peer-reviewed (but open access to reduce costs) scientific literature, relies on studies published in journals contributing to the understanding of environmental science, sustainability, and climate-related topics. Erik monitors information from government environmental agencies at the national and international levels to stay updated on regulatory changes, policy developments, and environmental impact assessments. He explores industry-specific reports, attends sustainability conferences and seminars, collaborates with research institutions focused on sustainability, engages in regular dialogues with internal and external stakeholders to gain on-the-ground insights. Erik excels in project management, stakeholder communication, and ensuring regulatory compliance, bringing a strategic and innovative approach to enhance overall environmental performance. He navigates the challenges of evolving sustainability standards and is driven by a commitment to creating positive environmental impacts through sustainable business practices.

Erik needs:

- Access to up to date and accurate literature and reports (IPCC, etc.). This is usually the starting point for his work;
- Climate policy documents, local legislation, etc.
- Access to environmental impact assessments
- To be able to find the right information at the right moment, and in particular eliminate any obsolete information. For this reason, all the data and information he can use for developing and implementing climate change adaptation strategies and plans, need to be available from his national climate centre (or environmental agency) that is the only valid authoritative source of climate data and information.
- For non-climate data, the approach is much more ad-hoc and depends on the clients.
- The need for computing and storage is very limited, and laptops are generally used. Cloud computing is unfamiliar, and it may not meet the varying security levels imposed by his clients.

Geo-ecologist specialised in climate extremes

Dr. Maya Andersson, a distinguished Geo-ecologist with an MSc and a specialisation in the analysis of climate extremes in climate models (PhD), has dedicated her career to unravelling the complexities of climate variability and its impacts on ecosystems. Proficient in geospatial analysis, GIS, and climate modelling, Maya excels in bridging the gap between climate science and ecology. In her current role, she conducts advanced analyses of climate extremes, contributes to interdisciplinary collaborations, and publishes research findings to inform conservation strategies. Recently, Maya has ventured into working with the finance sector, recognising the immense value of their data for climate risk assessment. However, the financial sector's reluctance to share data due to privacy and security concerns poses a significant challenge. Maya is keenly interested in being involved in a project focused on FAIR and open data sharing in support of climate change adaptation. She believes that such a project may not only contribute to the mission of climate

adaptation but also potentially provide solutions to unblock the current situation, particularly addressing the complexities of sharing data from the finance sector while ensuring privacy and security.

Maya needs:

- **Climate Model Data:** Access to high-quality and high-resolution climate model data is essential for Maya's analyses. This may involve collaboration with climate modelling institutions or access to reputable data repositories.
- **Geospatial Data:** Comprehensive geospatial datasets, including land cover, terrain, and ecosystem information, are crucial for Maya's work. Access to updated and accurate GIS data enhances the precision of her analyses.
- **Data Processing Software:** Maya may need specialised software for processing and analysing large datasets. Geographic Information System (GIS) software such as QGIS, statistical analysis tools, and programming languages like Python or R are valuable.
- **Climate Extremes Indices:** Specific software or tools designed for calculating climate extremes indices can aid Maya in identifying and quantifying extreme climate events within the data.
- **Financial data:** getting access to financial data is very challenging. There is a need to establish/use data governance that is acceptable for the financial sector. Privacy and security need to be guaranteed. Being able to anonymise datasets could be useful for developing the corresponding data analysis tools.
- **Computing Infrastructure:** Given the computational demands of climate modelling and geospatial analysis, Maya may benefit from access to high-performance computing (HPC) resources. This could involve collaboration with institutions or cloud computing services.
- **Storage Solutions:** Adequate storage capacity is essential for managing and archiving the extensive datasets involved in climate modelling. Maya may require secure and scalable storage solutions to accommodate her growing data needs.
- **FAIR Data Principles Implementation:** Maya's interest in FAIR and open data sharing necessitates the development or usage of platforms that adhere to these principles. This involves making data easily discoverable, accessible, and usable for collaboration.
- **Security Measures:** Given the sensitivity of financial data, Maya would need robust security measures to protect against unauthorised access and ensure compliance with privacy regulations. This would require a close collaboration with the finance sector to identify the current bottlenecks and understand their needs to develop or use solutions that are acceptable for both Maya and the finance sector.
- **Collaboration Tools:** Maya might benefit from tools that facilitate collaboration with interdisciplinary teams, enabling efficient communication and sharing of research findings. However, as mentioned above,
- **Training and Skill Development:** Training to learn how to use cloud computing and object storage is needed. She is also interested in learning how to FAIRify her data (and software, workflows, etc.) but she does not have much time to dedicate to it. She would prefer an approach where she learns by doing.

Experienced Project Manager for Climate Adaptation Projects

Sara Jensen, a Climate Risk and Adaptation Manager at Norconsult, holds a Master's degree in Environmental Science with over a decade of expertise in climate risk assessment and adaptation planning. Leading interdisciplinary teams, Sara orchestrates seamless collaborations, guiding comprehensive risk assessments and crafting tailored adaptation strategies. Committed to excellence, she ensures compliance with recognized standards like the [EU taxonomy](#) and [BREEAM](#), customising recommendations to meet the unique needs of each project. Sara navigates transition risks at the company level, mapping future scenarios to identify relevant risks and opportunities for clients' businesses. Through advanced modelling and prioritised risk management, she establishes decision-making frameworks for the effective implementation of climate adaptation measures. Sara's passion for creating resilient and sustainable solutions aligns with Norconsult's commitment to innovation and high standards, positioning her as a driving force in the dynamic field of climate risk and adaptation management.

Sara needs:

- Proficient in GIS and AutoCAD, Sara excels in mapping and follow-ups during both early and construction phases; specialising in contamination assessment in soil, water, and sediments.
- Tools to conduct risk and impact assessments, computes greenhouse gas emissions;
- Knows and applies BREEAM Infrastructure standards for sustainability.
- Uses visualisation and modelling tools to ensure project representation accuracy;
- Use tools to cooperate with external actors;
- Fluent in Norwegian (local language);
- Tools to translate environmental knowledge into actionable strategies for construction and building projects.

Climate Scientist working to deliver authoritative data for municipalities

Ole works at the Danish Meteorological Service that serves as the authoritative provider of [Denmark's Climate Atlas](#), a comprehensive nationwide tool forged from in-house data, insights from the IPCC, and diverse international databases. This Atlas offers critical data at municipality, drainage basin, and coastal stretch levels, projecting future changes in temperature, precipitation, extreme precipitation, relative sea level, and storm surge heights. Primarily tailored for municipalities, entrusted with climate adaptation responsibilities, the Climate Atlas extends its relevance to regions, utility companies, infrastructure, agriculture, emergency management, insurance, consultants, and various sectors. In collaboration with municipalities and stakeholders, this authoritative dataset aids in preemptive planning, allowing for precautions that safeguard citizens, infrastructure, and buildings against anticipated extreme weather conditions. While offering invaluable insights, the Climate Atlas emphasises the need for local knowledge integration to address specifics like flooding, water levels, and coastal erosion. As a visionary instrument, it showcases the future Danish climate throughout the century, depicting scenarios under different greenhouse gas emission levels. Presenting data at national and municipality levels, down to a 1 km grid scale, the Climate Atlas stands as an indispensable resource for informed decision-making and strategic climate change adaptation measures. Continuous updates, including additional data on relevant climate indicators, further fortify its role in shaping a resilient future.

Policy Advisor

Norbert, an experienced policy advisor within the Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations, brings a wealth of expertise in information management, CIO-advisory, portfolio management, enterprise architecture, and ICT. One of his current tasks is consulting a project on monitoring both indoor and outdoor temperatures of houses and the health and well-being of the inhabitants during heat waves.

Having engaged with individuals in 2024, Norbert recognizes the need to bridge existing data gaps. He champions the idea of creating a shared data space among governmental organisations, emphasising the importance of adhering to the FAIR principles—ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Norbert envisions this shared space as a catalyst for collaborative analysis, fostering a unified approach to leveraging data for informed decision-making.

Norbert strives to transform ideas into tangible solutions that not only monitor environmental conditions but also prioritise the holistic well-being of the people he serves. His journey involves navigating the intricacies of project establishment, securing funding, and championing a data-sharing paradigm that adheres to the highest standards of accessibility and utility.

Norbert needs:

- best practices for data sharing
- general and domain specific data standards
- overview of existing resources and solutions
- a solution architecture for one or more scenarios
- qualified contractors for solution development

Policy Consultant

Simon, a policy consultant in France, is working on developing a project that aims to monitor water quality in river-dominated ocean margins to support oyster farmers who are dealing with increasing threats to their business due to climate change. He sees the potential for this project to inform and enhance climate adaptation strategies and plans in his region. His ambition is to transform data and research into tangible solutions that prioritise the health of both local marine environments and the economic well-being of the oyster farming community. Despite his goals, Simon faces difficulties in identifying best practices for data sharing, data standards, and accessing existing resources, including data, methods, and related knowledge.

These challenges have made it difficult for him to draft a convincing proposal to stakeholders and secure the needed funding. Simon recognises the urgency of his project, given the potential impacts of climate change on the livelihoods of oyster farmers and the broader marine ecosystem. Simon is determined to overcome the obstacles he faces in order to ensure the sustainable future of his region's oyster farms. He believes that if he can concretely identify and demonstrate the current issues faced by the oyster farmers, outline the potential consequences if no action is taken, and propose measures to mitigate climate change and support the oyster farmers, he will be more likely to secure funding.

Simon needs:

- Identification of Best Practices: Clear guidelines or best practices for FAIR and open data sharing to ensure the quality and consistency of the information gathered.
- Access to Existing Resources: Assistance or tools to aid Simon in accessing existing resources, including data, methods, and related knowledge that are pivotal for the creation of his project.
- Data Standards Compliance: A comprehensive understanding of complying with data standards, ensuring the data collected will be used effectively and ethically.
- Concrete Evidence: Concrete and compelling evidence of the current challenges faced by the oyster farmers and the potential environmental impact if no action is taken.
- Mitigation Measures: Ideas for feasible measures to mitigate climate change effects and support the oyster farming community, which would form a key part of his proposal.
- Proposal Writing Support: Guidance or support in drafting a convincing project proposal that effectively communicates the urgency and benefits of the project, thereby optimising chances of securing necessary funding.
- Networking Opportunities: Opportunities to connect with potential stakeholders, experts or partners who could support his project, either financially or by providing relevant expertise.

Through addressing these needs, Simon can ultimately drive forward his ambition to translate data and research into tangible solutions that preserve the local marine environment and support the livelihoods of oyster farmers in the face of climate change.

Data Manager

Florence, who serves as the director of the Coastal Ecosystem Dynamics unit at IFREMER, is involved in a research project called RiOMar (River-dominated Ocean Margins), which aims to assess current coastal water quality and marine ecosystems, anticipate emerging climate impacts and prepare for stronger climate impacts by the end of the century. Florence leads a work package titled “Co-construction of environmental solutions with environmental managers and researchers - Mediation and communication to the stakeholders”. Her main duties involve promoting awareness of the RiOMar project and its findings among environmental managers from French regional authorities, achieved primarily through workshops and training.

She reckons that the project is centred around researchers and acknowledges the need to bridge existing data gaps: the RiOMar project will provide very valuable and high-resolution data that will be exploitable by scientists but unlikely to be mastered by environmental managers. There are no concrete plans and dedicated funding to go further and offer tools that could directly support environmental managers and help them to develop and implement concrete climate adaptation strategies and plans.

Florence needs:

- Knowledge Transfer Mechanism: A mechanism or platform that allows for the smooth transfer of complex, scientific data to environmental managers, ensuring they can not only understand but also utilise such information.
- Training Programs: Comprehensive training programs that equip environmental managers with the skills and knowledge required to interpret and apply the project's high-resolution data in their climate adaptation strategies.
- Data Simplification Tools: Development of tools for data simplification, conversion, or visualisation that make highly technical scientific data more digestible and practicable for non-expert stakeholders.

- Funding for Additional Resources: Secure additional funding to focus on the creation of tools and resources which are specifically designed to support environmental managers.
- Co-Creation Opportunities: Facilitate opportunities to co-conceive environmental solutions with environmental managers, encouraging a more democratised and inclusive approach to climate adaptation.
- Communicative Strategies: Effective methods or strategies to communicate the aims, methodology, and results of the RiOMar project to stakeholders, promoting broader understanding and buy-in.
- Bridging Data Gaps: Identify strategies or employ tools to bridge existing data gaps, ensuring complete and reliable data coverage to inform robust climate adaptation planning.

By meeting these needs, Florence can ensure that not only researchers but also environmental managers at regional authorities can fully capitalise on the valuable data produced by the RiOMar project and use it to develop and implement effective climate change adaptation strategies.

Environmental Engineer

Tiago, an environmental engineer holding a Ph.D. in Environmental Sciences, specialises in climate change adaptation with a focus on understanding decision-making processes and managing uncertainty. Tiago leverages extensive experience in both policy and applied aspects of climate adaptation in Portugal and Europe. His practical knowledge spans the complexities of climate risk assessment, adaptation measure identification, and seamless integration into policy and planning frameworks. In his work, Tiago faces challenges related to interdisciplinary collaboration and the need to access data from various domains, stored in diverse repositories and sources. He aspires to achieve a more integrated view to facilitate a holistic understanding of climate-related information. Despite considerable efforts and progress made to provide comprehensive and easily navigable access to climate adaptation-related data and knowledge, as seen in portals like ClimateAdapt, Tiago observes that many stakeholders still struggle to grasp the necessary information for developing relevant and scientifically-grounded climate adaptation strategies and plans. He firmly believes that embracing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles and open data sharing, especially through machine-actionable approaches, can be a game-changer for the climate adaptation community. This approach has the potential to empower a broader spectrum of actors to take effective steps towards efficient climate adaptation planning and implementation.

Tiago needs:

- Interdisciplinary Collaboration Platform: A dedicated platform that facilitates more efficient interdisciplinary collaboration, effectively bringing together data and insights from diverse domains.
- Access to Diverse Data Repositories: Simplified and streamlined access to diverse data repositories and sources to accumulate a holistic view of climate-related information.
- Machine-Actionable Approaches: The adoption and integration of machine-actionable approaches such as AI and machine learning to ease data processing, interpretation, and application, hence accelerating the process of climate adaptation planning and implementation.
- Education for Stakeholders: Education and support for stakeholders to understand and effectively use the data and knowledge provided in portals like ClimateAdapt for developing climate adaptation strategies and plans.
- Policy Integration Support: Insight and direction on how to seamlessly integrate climate risk assessment and adaptation measures into policy and planning frameworks.

- FAIR Principles Advocacy: Active advocacy and support for the adoption of FAIR principles and open data sharing within the climate adaptation community.
- User-Friendly Navigation and Interfaces: Development of more user-friendly interfaces, including data portals and tools, that enable stakeholders to easily find and navigate climate adaptation-related data and knowledge.

Interdisciplinary researcher

Sukaina is an interdisciplinary senior researcher with a unique blend of skills in social anthropology and computer science. Sukaina co-led climate service initiatives and currently plays a pivotal role in coordinating the strategic and technical development of the weADAPT global platform, a critical hub for climate change adaptation initiatives. Sukaina is deeply engaged in advancing urban adaptation in southern Africa, fostering connections among European communities focused on climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction, and contributing to the development of climate change adaptation taxonomies and climate services. Sukaina's expertise extends to global platforms, as evidenced by her role as a contributing author to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, Working Group II, on Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Her influence is felt not only in academic circles but also in shaping policy discussions at the international level.

Sukaina's multidisciplinary research demands a seamless integration of qualitative and quantitative data. The FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) play a pivotal role in Sukaina's work, ensuring that data is easily discoverable, accessible to diverse stakeholders, interoperable across systems, and reusable for various research endeavours.

For Sukaina, the mission adaptation to climate change relies on the collaborative efforts of diverse stakeholders, and FAIR and open data sharing serve as the cornerstone for achieving impactful and scalable results.

Sukaina needs:

- FAIR Tools and Training: As a senior interdisciplinary researcher, Sukaina likely needs tools that support the implementation of FAIR principles, as well as training for her and her team on how to use these tools efficiently.
- Collaborative Platforms: In order to foster connections and collaborate effectively across diverse stakeholder groups, Sukaina requires platforms that provide seamless integration for both qualitative and quantitative data.
- Interoperable Systems: Since her work demands drawing from multiple domains, systems that allow for interoperability (the ability for computer systems to exchange and use information) are essential.
- Data Accessibility Solutions: Meeting the demands of her diverse roles requires streamlined solutions for making data easily discoverable and accessible to multiple stakeholders, from academic researchers to policymakers.
- Policy Impact Support: Given her influence in shaping policy discussions, Sukaina would benefit from support or tools that help to communicate the implications of her research to a policy audience, such as data visualisation or translation tools.
- Reproducible Research Strategies: Given the principle of 'reusability' in FAIR, Sukaina would need strategies and infrastructures that support reproducible research, allowing other researchers to effectively build upon existing findings.

Conclusion

From the user personas collected, it is clear that each persona has unique needs when it comes to accessing, understanding, and utilising data for climate adaptation efforts. At the same time, commonalities emerge across the personas, indicating areas of shared need and emphasis. These commonalities include the requirement for platforms and tools to facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, simplified access to diverse data repositories, ease of integration for qualitative and quantitative data, measures to enhance data discoverability and accessibility across systems, and training to understand and effectively apply FAIR principles.

The personas also highlight the specific challenges faced by individuals from different roles and backgrounds, from navigating the complexities of data sharing for climate change adaptation to vulnerabilities in the face of data gaps. Above all, there exists an urgency to embrace and implement FAIR principles which underlie much of the personas' expressed needs.

Based on these extensive interviews and the unique insights gained from each persona, we have decided to further enhance the comprehensiveness and depth of our HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 project proposal by including concrete case studies. These case studies are specifically selected to reflect the diverse scenarios and challenges highlighted by our personas, such as addressing data gaps, facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration, or ensuring data security in sensitive sectors.

Moreover, to strengthen the practical impact and real-world applicability of these case studies, we have extended invitations to the corresponding interviewees to join our consortium. We believe that their first-hand experiences and in-depth knowledge, as reflected in the personas, will significantly enrich our consortium. Their participation allows direct incorporation of their unique perspectives and provides us the benefit of real-time feedback and solution validation as we progress with our project proposal.

This approach of not only recognizing and understanding but also directly involving our stakeholders deeply aligns with our commitment to collaborative and inclusive climate adaptation efforts. We are enthusiastic about the potential synergies and the impact these collaborations can create towards designing scientifically sound climate adaptation strategies.

In conclusion, these findings will prove invaluable in shaping the objectives of the HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 project proposal. The insights across the personas provide clear and concrete directions on the range of needs and solutions that should be addressed in the proposal. By aligning the project objectives in tune with these needs and providing appropriate solutions, the proposal stands to make a significant impact in the realm of climate adaptation strategies, plans, and policies.